

HOW TO BECOME A GOOD LISTENER

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Annotation: This article highlights some innovative strategies for improving listening skill of English Language of secondary level students. Effective Listening in English language, guiding the students towards effective oral communication, is the problem with all the ESL students at secondary level and as such it creates problem for English language teachers. The objective of the study was to help the English language teachers and students to overcome this problem by showing the results of application of innovative strategies for improving English language listening skill.

Keywords: innovative strategies, listening comprehension, temptation, language listening skill, challenges, frustrate.

Listening is the ability to accurately receive and interpret messages in the communication process. Listening is key to all effective communication. Without the ability to listen effectively, messages are easily misunderstood. As a result, communication breaks down and the sender of the message can easily become frustrated or irritated. If there is one communication skill you should aim to master, then listening is it. Listening is so important that many top employers provide listening skills training for their employees. This is not surprising when you consider that good listening skills can lead to better customer satisfaction, greater productivity with fewer mistakes, and increased sharing of information that in turn can lead to more creative and innovative work.

Listening often is the most important way to improve your listening skills. Enjoy the listening possibilities offered by the Internet and remember to relax. Despite its obvious importance to language learning, the listening skill was for a

long time relegated to a marginal place in foreign language curricula. With the advent of communicative language teaching and the focus on proficiency, the learning and teaching of listening started to receive more attention. However, listening is not yet fully integrated into the curriculum and needs to be given more "prime time" in class and homework. For learners, listening presents a challenge for a variety of reasons, among which are the following:

- Listening involves multiple modes: Listening involves the interpersonal and interpretive modes of communication. It requires the listener to assume either a participative role in face-to-face conversations, or a non-participative role in listening to other people speak or present
- Listening involves all varieties of language: In addition to listening to lectures and presentations in academic and formal settings, learners have also to partake or listen to exchanges that involve various levels of colloquialism.
- Listening involves "altered" and "reduced" language forms: In addition to dealing with the vocabulary and structures of the language, listeners have to learn to comprehend reduced forms of the language (e.g., I wanna go, Just a sec).
- Listening involves variable rates of delivery

Unlike a reading text that is at the learner's control, a listening text is constantly moving and at variable speeds that often cannot be controlled by the listener, because of all these factors, listening activities often create high levels of anxiety and stress among learners that can interfere with comprehension. For teachers as well, addressing listening in the language classroom poses some challenges. As a language teacher, one of your tasks will be to develop a vision of where listening fits within your teaching. As you progress through this module, continue to think of how you might plan to approach listening activities and what goals and expectations to set for your students.

Most effective leaders and managers realise the importance of acquiring good listening skills, so if you are aiming to climb the ladder of success, this is something

you need to take seriously. The consequences of not listening carefully could be disastrous.

Good listening skills will give you an edge in life and at work. However, if you are to become an effective listener, it's going to take more than just desire and enthusiasm — it's going to take a huge conscious effort.

Here are my suggestions for how you can improve your listening skills:

1. Prepare to listen. Clear your mind so that your attention is assured.
2. Avoid pre-judgment. Do not pre-judge the speaker because of appearance or occupation, and do not jump to any conclusions before hearing what is said.
3. Be open-minded. Appreciate the speaker's point of view and accept that it may not necessarily agree with your own.
4. Establish eye contact. This shows that you are listening, as does your posture and your facial expressions.
5. Don't interrupt. Try to keep emotions out of it and hold any counter-arguments until the speaker has finished.
6. Watch for signals. Pick up aspects that the speaker considers important by watching posture and gestures, as well as listening to intonation in the speaker's voice. This is like listening to the 'music' as well as to the words.
7. Judge content, not delivery. Appraise the content instead of the speaker. Consider the main points and ask if they make sense.
8. Extract key points. Pick out and repeat to yourself some key words or phrases. This will help to fix in your mind what is being said.
9. Give feedback. Learn to give positive feedback non-verbally, perhaps by nodding or smiling, to let the speaker know you are following what is being said. Be alert and make an appropriate comment or ask a question if it will help your understanding.
10. Block out distractions. Fight distractions and competing thoughts, by working hard at listening. You may need to close doors, turn off a television or radio, or move closer to the speaker.

Listening is vitally important, sadly undertaught, physically and mentally taxing, and in the aftermath of Covid-19 has never been more difficult. As we close in on a third year of unprecedented upheaval in work and life, employees and managers alike have more questions than ever — concerns that they may find it difficult to articulate for a variety of reasons, from mental fog to the sheer novelty of the situation. When this happens, take a moment to listen closely. Consider the questioner, not simply the question. Now is the time for leaders to really listen, understand the context, resist the temptation to respond with generic answers, and recognize your own listening limitations — and improve on them. Have compassion for yourself — you can't scream at your own brain like a drill sergeant and whip that raw grey matter into shape. What you can do is recognize your weak points and make the necessary adjustments.

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